

The Attitudes of People Towards Entrepreneurship Knowledge in the Selected Public Markets in Kasama District of Northern Province of Zambia

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Abstract – The cardinal purpose of carrying out this research project an enquiry into the attitudes of people towards entrepreneurship knowledge: a case study of selected public markets in Kasama district of Northern Province of Zambia The research will be carefully guided by specific objectives in avoidance of irrelevance and deviance. In this research three types of questionnaires will be precisely employed: One type designed for traders, another for directors and the other one for general dealers. Moreover, it will be a descriptive research study. The research study will also use qualitative and quantitative techniques; the findings will be analyzed using reliable instruments and procedures so as to attain the desirable results. The data will be collected from the recipients using interviews and questionnaires templates. The target recipient population will be 120 and the working sample will be 50 as representation consisting of: 15 learners picked by sampling technique from the three selected public markets, 15 general dealers, 3 firm administrators, 5 officials from Business community and 10 parents of the traders at the selected and targeted public markets in Kasama district. The data will be tabulated and presented as percentages and averages for a comprehensive data distribution. Furthermore, recommendations will be made so that the government may implement the findings with a view of providing the necessary resources by subsidizing the cost of entrepreneurship education especially to vulnerable learners hence equal opportunities and proactive attitude towards entrepreneurship knowledge to all children in Zambian entrepreneurial ventures in far and near locations.

Keywords – E-SERVQUAL, Online Shopping Platforms, Service Quality, Consumer Perception, Anna Nagar, Chennai.

I. INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides you with an overview of entrepreneurship and of the language of entrepreneurship. The challenges associated with defining entrepreneur and entrepreneurship are explored, as is an overview of how entrepreneurship can be studied.

The objective is to enable you to apply current concepts in entrepreneurship to the evaluation of entrepreneurs, their ventures, and the venturing environment. You will develop skills, including the capability to add value in the new venture sector of the economy. You will acquire and practice evaluation skills useful in consulting, advising, and making new venture decisions.

Entrepreneurs and Entrepreneurship

Considerations Influencing Definitions of Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship

It is necessary to be able to determine exactly who entrepreneurs are before we can, among other things, study them, count them, provide special loans for them, and calculate how and how much they contribute to our economy.

- Does someone need to start a business from scratch to be called an entrepreneur?
- Can we call someone an entrepreneur if they bought an ongoing business from someone else or took over the operations of a family business from their parents?
- If someone starts a small business and never needs to hire employees, can they be called an entrepreneur?

- If someone buys a business but hires professional managers to run it so they don't have to be involved in the operations, are they an entrepreneur?
- Is someone an entrepreneur if they buy into a franchise so they can follow a well-established formula for running the operation?
- Is someone an entrepreneur because of what they do or because of how they think?
- Can someone be an entrepreneur without owning their own business?
- Can a person be an entrepreneur because of the nature of the work that they do within a large corporation?

It is also necessary to fully understand what we mean by entrepreneurship before we can study the concept.

Gartner (1990) identified 90 attributes that showed up in definitions of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship provided by entrepreneurs and other experts in the field. The following are a few of these attributes:

- Innovation – Does a person need to be innovative to be considered an entrepreneur? Can an activity be considered to be entrepreneurial if it is not innovative?
- Activities – What activities does a person need to do to be considered an entrepreneur?
- Creation of a new business – Does someone need to start a new business to be considered to be an entrepreneur, or can someone who buys a business, buys into a franchise, or takes over an existing family business be considered an entrepreneur?
- Starts an innovative venture within an established organization – Can someone who works within an existing organization that they don't own be considered

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an entrepreneur if they start an innovative venture for their organization?

- Creation of a not-for-profit business – Can a venture be considered to be entrepreneurial if it is a not-for-profit, or should only for-profit businesses be considered entrepreneurial?

After identifying the 90 attributes, Gartner (1990) went back to the entrepreneurs and other experts for help in clustering the attributes into themes that would help summarize what people concerned with entrepreneurship thought about the concept. He ended up with the following eight entrepreneurship themes:

1. The Entrepreneur – The entrepreneur theme is the idea that entrepreneurship involves individuals with unique personality characteristics and abilities (e.g., risk-taking, locus of control, autonomy, perseverance, commitment, vision, creativity). Almost 50% of the respondents rated these characteristics as not important to a definition of entrepreneurship (Gartner, 1990, p. 21, 24).

- “The question that needs to be addressed is: Does entrepreneurship involve entrepreneurs (individuals with unique characteristics)?” (Gartner, 1990, p. 25).

2. Innovation – The innovation theme is characterized as doing something new as an idea, product, service, market, or technology in a new or established organization. The innovation theme suggests that innovation is not limited to new ventures, but recognized as something which older and/or larger organizations may undertake as well (Gartner, 1990, p. 25). Some of the experts Gartner questioned believed that it was important to include innovation in definitions of entrepreneurship and others did not think it was as important.

- “Does entrepreneurship involve innovation?” (Gartner, 1990, p. 25).

3. Organization Creation – The organization creation theme describes the behaviors involved in creating organizations. This theme described acquiring and integrating resource attributes (e.g., Brings resources to bear, integrates opportunities with resources, mobilizes resources, gathers resources) and attributes that described creating organizations (new venture development and the creation of a business that adds value). (Gartner, 1990, p. 25)

- “Does entrepreneurship involve resource acquisition and integration (new venture creation activities)?” (Gartner, 1990, p. 25)

4. Creating Value – This theme articulated the idea that entrepreneurship creates value. The attributes in this factor indicated that value creation might be represented by transforming a business, creating a new business growing a business, creating wealth, or destroying the status quo.

- “Does entrepreneurship involve creating value?” (Gartner, 1990, p. 25).

5. Profit or Nonprofit

- “Does entrepreneurship involve profit-making organizations only?” (Gartner, 1990, p. 25)?

6. Growth

- Should a focus on growth be a characteristic of entrepreneurship?

7. Uniqueness – This theme suggested that entrepreneurship must involve uniqueness. Uniqueness was characterized by attributes such as a special way of thinking, a vision of accomplishment, ability to see situations in terms of unmet needs, and creates a unique combination.

- “Does entrepreneurship involve uniqueness?” (Gartner, 1990, p. 26).

8. The Owner-Manager – Some of the respondents questioned by Gartner (1990) did not believe that small mom-and-pop types of businesses should be considered to be entrepreneurial. Some respondents felt that an important element of a definition of entrepreneurship was that a venture be owner-managed.

- To be entrepreneurial, does a venture need to be owner-managed?

Examples of Definitions of Entrepreneur

An entrepreneur can be described as “one who creates a new business in the face of risk and uncertainty for the purpose of achieving profit and growth by identifying significant opportunities and assembling the necessary resources to capitalize on them” (Zimmerer & Scarborough, 2008, p. 5).

An entrepreneur is “one who organizes, manages, and assumes the risks of a business or enterprise” (Entrepreneur, n.d.).

Examples of Definitions of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship can be defined as a field of business that seeks to understand how opportunities to create something new (e.g., new products or services, new markets, new production processes or raw materials, new ways of organizing existing technologies) arise and are discovered or created by specific persons, who then use various means to exploit or develop them, thus producing a wide range of effects (Baron, Shane, & Reuber, 2008, p. 4)

A concise definition of entrepreneurship “is that it is the process of pursuing opportunities without limitation by resources currently in hand” (Brooks, 2009, p. 3) and “the process of doing something new and something different for the purpose of creating wealth for the individual and adding value to society” (Kao, 1993, p. 70)

The Evolution of Entrepreneurship Thought

This section includes an overview of how entrepreneurship has evolved to the present day.

The following timeline shows some of the most influential entrepreneurship scholars and the schools of thought (French, English, American, German, and Austrian) their perspectives helped influence and from which their ideas evolved. Schools of thought are essentially groups of people who might or might not have personally known each other, but who shared common beliefs or philosophies.

Figure 1 – Historical and Evolutionary Entrepreneurship Thought (Illustration by Lee A. Swanson)

The Earliest Entrepreneurship

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The function, if not the name, of the entrepreneur is probably as old as the institutions of barter and exchange. But only after economic markets became an intrusive element of society did the concept take on pivotal importance. Many economists have recognized the pivotal role of the entrepreneur in a market economy. Yet despite his central importance in economic activity, the entrepreneur has been a shadowy and elusive figure in the history of economic theory (Hebert & Link, 2009, p. 1).

Historically those who acted similarly to the ways we associate with modern day entrepreneurs – namely those who strategically assume risks to seek economic (or other) gains – were military leaders, royalty, or merchants. Military leaders planned their campaigns and battles while assuming significant risks, but by doing so they also stood to gain economic benefits if their strategies were successful. Merchants, like Marco Polo who sailed out of Venice in the late 1200s to search for a trade route to the Orient, also assumed substantial risks in the hope of becoming wealthy (Hebert & Link, 2009).

The entrepreneur, who was also called adventurer, projector, and undertaker during the eighteenth century, was not always viewed in a positive light (Hebert & Link, 2009).

Entrepreneurial Uniqueness

Efforts to teach entrepreneurship have included descriptions of entrepreneurial uniqueness based on personality, behavioural, and cognitive traits (Chell, 2008; Duening, 2010).

Personality characteristics

o Three personality characteristics of entrepreneurs that are often cited are:

- Need for achievement
- Internal locus of control (a belief by an individual that they are in control of their own destiny)
- Risk-taking propensity
- Behavioural traits
- Cognitive skills of successful entrepreneurs

Past studies of personality characteristics and behavioural traits have not been overly successful at identifying entrepreneurial uniqueness.

As it turned out, years of painstaking research along this line has not borne significant fruit. It appears that there are simply not any personality characteristics that are either essential to, or defining of, entrepreneurs that differ systematically from non-entrepreneurs.... Again, investigators proposed a number of behavioural candidates as emblematic of entrepreneurs. Unfortunately, this line of research also resulted in a series of dead ends as examples of successful entrepreneurial behaviours had equal counterparts among samples of non-entrepreneurs. As with the personality characteristic school of thought before it, the behavioural trait school of thought became increasingly difficult to support (Duening, 2010, p. 4-5).

This shed doubt on the value of trying to change personality characteristics or implant new entrepreneurial behaviours through educational programs in an effort to promote entrepreneurship.

New research, however, has resurrected the idea that there might be some value in revisiting personality traits as a topic of study. Additionally, Duening (2010) and has suggested that an important approach to teaching and learning about entrepreneurship is to focus on the “cognitive skills that successful entrepreneurs seem uniquely to possess and deploy” (p. 2). In the next sections we consider the new research on entrepreneurial personality traits and on entrepreneurial cognitions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

The chapter consists of definition for key concepts of the research problem, empirical literature reviews, theoretical/conceptual framework and knowledge gap.

The Concept of Entrepreneurship

Literature on different aspects of entrepreneurship shows that the word, entrepreneur, is derived from the French word entrepreneur, which means to do something. Entrepreneurship has been defined in many ways by different scholars. Entrepreneurship is understood as a dynamic and social process where people, individually or in collaboration, identify opportunities and utilize them to reshape ideas into practical and goal oriented activities in social, cultural or economic contexts (Swedish National Board for Industrial and Technical Development, 2004). Here entrepreneurship is understood as a non-static social process where people (either individually or as a group) identify opportunities and take advantage of them.

In addition, Chigunta (2002) defined entrepreneurship as an innovative way of managing opportunities and process of creating something new with value by devoting the required time and effort to gain economic independence and rewards (monetary or non-monetary) and achieve satisfaction. Entrepreneurship is understood as the driving force for initiating business ideas and mobilizing human, financial and physical resources for establishing and expanding enterprises and creating jobs. The business economist Muhlenbock (2004) views entrepreneurship as something that is conducted both by individuals and in organizations and that it is process that creates contacts and is characterized by a specific way of acting which can take place in different fields.

In other words, entrepreneurship is the process of establishing a business enterprise and entrepreneurs who possess the capacity to generate employment for them as well as others. Innovation and entrepreneurship are tightly coupled concepts. Innovation involves designing new ways of conceptualizing, developing and producing products. How new ideas are converted into products through entrepreneurship is an added dimension, which is

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sometimes is said to be a mindset required to convert innovation into a real business situation for delivering benefits to stakeholders. An entrepreneur is one who organizes, operates and assumes the risks in a business venture in an expectation of making a profit.

Thus, an entrepreneur is a person who gets things done, starts a venture on his or her own and is able to create something that produces an outcome such as wealth. Entrepreneurship is seen as a key driver to any country's economy. Wealth and a high majority of jobs are created by small businesses started by entrepreneurially minded individuals, many of whom go on to create big businesses. People who are exposed to entrepreneurship frequently have more opportunity to exercise creative freedoms, higher self-esteem, and greater sense of control over their own lives.

Entrepreneurship also contributes to social cohesion, by increasing employment, economic reward and work satisfaction (The International Design Technology Conference, DesTech2015, 29th of June – 1st of July 2015). Moreover, Mubanga, YuHock , Mahbub, Sentri, Mutale & Mulenga (2019) defined entrepreneurship as the ability/capacity and eagerness to develop, organize and manage a business undertaking on its possible risks with a view to earning a profit. From the foregoing entrepreneurship is understood as an activity that involves designing, launching and running a new enterprise, in the initial stages, it may start as a small business, with the potential to grow and make profit.

Entrepreneurship is considered a central force of economic development because it generates growth and serves as a vehicle for innovation and change. It is necessary to understand the importance and usefulness of the concept of entrepreneurship in order to be able to transmit to the young generation the useful, necessary and sufficient entrepreneurial information that determines change and innovation in the modern world. Among the various definitions of entrepreneurship, this paper adopts a definition along the lines proposed by Stevenson (1989) who viewed entrepreneurship as the process by which individuals become aware of business ownership as an option or viable alternative, develop ideas for business, learn the process of becoming an entrepreneur and undertake the initiation and development of a business.

Drawing upon the above definition of entrepreneurship, and for the purpose of this paper, entrepreneurship is understood as the practical application of enterprising qualities, such as initiative, innovation, creativity, and risk-taking into the work environment (either in self-employment or employment in small start-up firms) using the appropriate skills necessary for success in that environment and culture (Schnurr and Newing, 1997). This is in line with Scurt and Semeniuc (2015) who indicated that entrepreneurship creates wealth, new job opportunities, improves quality of life and is a better solution for unemployment.

Learners' Perceptions of the Importance of Entrepreneurship Education

Some recent studies on the outcomes of EE in Europe pointed to positive correlations between EE and perceived entrepreneurial skills (Riese, 2011, Johansen & Clausen, 2011). One of the control group study indicated that the correlations between EE and perceived entrepreneurial abilities were strong among pupils in most European schools. Most pupils had significantly higher positive perception of EE, entrepreneurial knowledge and skills (Johansen & Mathisen, 2012). These positive perceptions of pupils about EE were probably caused by the promotion of EE in secondary schools and higher education institutions across Europe.

The purpose of EE were perceived as that of promoting general entrepreneurial abilities such as willingness to take initiative, innovativeness and creativity, willingness to take risks, self-confidence, ability to collaborate and social skills. However, the Swedish teachers and pupils were still struggling with the division of entrepreneurship into an entrepreneurial and an enterprising part (Seikkula-Leino, Ruskovaara, Hannula & Saarivirta, 2012). In South Africa, EE was perceived as that which nurtures viable and sustainable businesses that Promote economic growth, job creation and the general prosperity of nation (Nicolaidis, 2011). Due to this perception South Africa has seen the need for education institutions to play the lead role in addressing school leavers 'employability challenges and the entrepreneurship education crisis. As Govender (2008) stated that, there is a need to promote entrepreneurship activity among students as this in turn creates skilled and opportunity driven entrepreneurs. The recent studies in South African secondary schools showed that most of learners had strong understanding of entrepreneurship and had strong desire to do businesses (Nicolaidis, 2011).

From the Zambian context, EE is perceived as the solution to the job crisis. The introduction of EE in schools was done as a means of mitigation of the job crisis in the formal sector. Despite an increasing number of universities in Zambia offering EE since the year 2000, less than 5% of university students engage in EE. In developed economies like the EU, the EE engagement rates are higher i.e. between 16% and 23% (Consultants, 2008, Johansen & Mathisen, 2012). Chimanga (2007) surveyed 38 graduate entrepreneurs and observed that 57.4% of graduates who owned and managed registered businesses were aged between 22 and 39 years and that the majority of these started businesses as a result of lack of employment opportunities. The low engagement rate in Zambia is perhaps because of lack of empirical evidence on the impact of EE in Zambia (Fayolle and Liñán, 2014; Küttim et al., 2014, Chigunta, 2017).

There was no traceable study in Zambia which has been conducted to examine the perceptions of pupils towards EE in secondary schools as most of the studies conducted concentrated on higher education students and graduates.

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The knowledge of the perceptions of the pupils towards EE can play an important role in coming up with the best pedagogies in the delivery of EE programmes in schools. This is very important because some pupils drop out at secondary school level, they don't reach higher institutions like colleges and universities.

The Attitudes of Learners towards Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education is viewed as a form of training in entrepreneurial knowledge, behaviour, attitudes and skills (Pulka, Rikwentshe, & Ibrhain (2014)). The students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship education can be measured in terms of three components of entrepreneurship attitudes namely cognitive, affective and behavioral attitude components (Pulka, Rikwentshe & Ibrhain, 2014). The cognitive component relates to beliefs, thoughts and knowledge students have about entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship education that shape their attitudes and behaviours (Amdam, 2011). The affective component relates to feelings and emotions about entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship education, that is, how a person sees the desirability or relevance of something and hence whether eventually they either like it or not (Pulka et al, 2014).

The behavioural component relates to actions, overt responses and willingness to respond to or accept something (Mani, 2008). Many research revealed that entrepreneurs are not naturally born but made through their environment and experiences as they learning and learning, being affected by guardian, mentors, tutors, instructors role model during their development process (Texeira and Davy -2008). Some studies in Europe indicated that students had positive attitudes towards EE, though differences between gender and institutions continued to be significant in post completion of the course. The central aim of the studies was to investigate whether participation in taught EE has a positive impact on attitudes towards entrepreneurship in general and as a career option. In particular, the research suggested that the French and Polish students had positive attitudes towards EE (Bosma and Harding, 2006).

Gerba (2012) stated that having a positive attitude towards EE implies having an appreciation of EE as an important means of developing entrepreneurial skills in people which skills manifest through creative strategies, innovative tactics, uncanny identification of trends and opportunities in the market. Further studies across European schools indicated that the integration of EE in subjects as a project or topic and focus on creativity, initiative and self-reliance, significantly increased the positive attitudes of students towards EE (European Commission, 2012). This is in line with Basu and Virik (2008), who found that EE improves attitudes of students towards entrepreneurship. Other studies in Botswana of university students also indicated that they also had positive attitudes towards EE and showed the understanding and appreciated the role that the EE programmes played in developing entrepreneurship knowledge and skills and participated in the EE programmes.

In addition, the students showed willingness to engage in entrepreneurship activities after completing school (Rudhumbu, Svatwa, Munyanyiwa & Mutsau, 2016). Furthermore, one of the researches conducted on graduates and school drop outs in Zambia indicated that the graduates and school drop outs preferred being in formal employment rather than starting up a business or any entrepreneurial investment (Chigunta & Chisupa, 2013). This study also indicated that many young people would engage themselves into business as a second option after failing to get a formal job. Another study done on the selected Zambian universities to identify the students' attitudes and awareness about EE revealed that the students had strong favorable attitudes towards EE. The students indicated positive attitudes towards EE by showing the willingness to become entrepreneurs and showed understanding that EE would help them in achieving their goals (Subburaj, 2018). However, little is known about the attitudes of pupils towards EE in secondary schools in Zambia.

The Practicability of Entrepreneurship Education in Learning Institutions:

The aim of introducing EE in schools is to promote specific entrepreneurial abilities like knowledge of how to start and run a business and about innovative processes in existing enterprises. In the early years of education, EE is integrated in subjects as a project or topic and focus on creativity, initiative and self-reliance. From the upper secondary level, EE is also taught as a separate subject and focuses more on learning the skills and know-how of setting up and running a business (European Commission, 2012). However, EE still relies heavily on the enthusiasm and commitment of individual teachers and the learners involved. In Europe, EE is implemented as a separate subject, a topic in existing subjects, or integrated into subjects through the use of the project method (EACEA Eurydice, 2012, Johansen & Schanke, 2012). The European Commission (2005, 2012) considers mini-companies best practice 'in EE.

In their assessment of mini-companies, the Commission comments on the lack of robust evaluations that highlight the added value of participation in mini-companies. Parallel to the research design in the study used, the Commission argues that the acquisition of competences and attitudes among participants in mini-companies was compared with information from groups of non-participants. The use of mini-companies in many European countries showed many benefits like that of making pupils acquire business skills, exhibit their creativity, develop enthusiasm and self-confidence, learn how to work in a team and value the importance of EE. It was also noted that participation in mini-companies generated enthusiasm and motivation, even among pupils who lack motivation in more traditional subjects. In addition working within mini-companies fulfilled many of the goals and targets set for other subjects, and added value in relation to all subjects' (European Commission, 2005).

In Malaysia, most of the teaching approaches are generic and fail to inculcate entrepreneurship's true value. The

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research findings also indicated that lectures were the most common and popular methodology in the delivery of EE over other methods such as business simulation, role play, and case studies (Yusoff, Zainol & Mohamed, 2015). Teaching methods that are teacher-centered may be appropriate in the context of explaining theoretical concepts; however, such a method is not able to provide actual experience and consequently the knowledge fails to be put into practice and students' learning experience is not maximized. Similarly a research which was conducted in South Africa indicated that the implementation of EE in secondary schools needed numerous initiatives and efforts of various role-players to take keen interest in promoting the growth of entrepreneurship education in South Africa.

The South African Curriculum of 2005, specifically included EE, which was to be based on sound pedagogical principles which should, in the long run, undoubtedly contribute to the full development of learners and the social wellbeing of the nation at large through the involvement of learners in active practical's (Mande Nchu, 2015). However, the result of this study suggested that the promotion of EE was less fruitful than what the policy discourse implied. The study further suggested that there was need to engage learners in practices which could motivate their positive attitudes towards the importance of EE. In Zambia the research from colleges and universities also indicated that the EE offered was theory based, less practical in nature and was anchored on training students for employment in the public sector (Phiri, Mbozi & Kalimaposo, 2018). However, it must be recognized that the public sector cannot absorb all the graduates in formal employment hence the need to foster entrepreneurial education for graduates to grow the informal sector. It must be noted that, in Zambia, the pupils' perceptions of the practicability of EE in secondary schools remained unknown.

Perceptions of the Challenges of Implementing Entrepreneurship Education Curriculum in Learning Institutions.

Entrepreneurship education is seen as activities aiming to improve the comprehensive quality of learners, enhance their ability to adapt to the society; to cultivate the entrepreneurial spirit, and enhance students' entrepreneurial skills (Watson, 2008). However the implementation of EE curriculum has met a number of challenges. A research which was conducted in Finland by Jaana (2011) indicated lack of well trained teachers who could effectively offer EE as one of the challenge of implementing EE curriculum. The teachers surveyed seemed to know the aims of entrepreneurship education, but their knowledge of its contents and working methods was very limited. They knew what they should implement but they did not know how. The research further suggested that teachers needed some basic training in best methods of implementing EE curriculum. A similar research which was conducted in Nigeria by Charlie (2013) revealed that the challenges of implementing EE curriculum in colleges and

universities were among others; poor infrastructure, inadequate funding, faulty foundation (new curriculum lacks necessary foundation) and inadequate and lack of high level manpower for effective teaching and learning of entrepreneurship education in the country.

This research recommended for increase in funding the implementation of EE curriculum at all levels of education (from primary, secondary school to tertiary education) and training of personnel involved in teaching and learning of EE. In Zambia, Subburaj (2018) conducted a survey among university students which indicated that the students had the challenges of resources and lack of sound and qualitative entrepreneurship curriculum to promote the entrepreneurship education. The research further suggested that the Zambian universities should strive to find resources, include sound and qualitative entrepreneurship Curriculum and its related activities to their students which would lead to development of favorable attitude towards entrepreneurship. The pupils' perceptions of the challenges of implementing entrepreneurship education curriculum in secondary schools in Zambia were still unknown as most studies seem to have concentrated on colleges and universities.

Management of Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship is the driving force of every market economy (Davies, 2001:32) whereby the entrepreneur aims at making a profit through the mobilization and coordination of all factors of production. Entrepreneurship is revitalizing and restructuring economies and it involves having a vision, creativity and innovation (Gouws, 2002:42). Small businesses in the United States of America are thriving, in providing over 20 million jobs in the last decade. Entrepreneurship is responsible for almost zero unemployment in countries like Indonesia, Malaysia and Singapore (Gouws, 2002:42). The economic recession and high unemployment rates suffered by many industrialized countries have revived their interest in Entrepreneurship (Garavan & O'Connell, 1994:3).

This has tended to increase the involvement of politicians and policy makers to focus on entrepreneurship as the answer to curbing unemployment and increasing economic growth (Garavan & O'Connell, 1994:13). With entrepreneurship being the focus of every economy, entrepreneurship education too has gained attention in these economies. Entrepreneurship education is defined by Isaacs, Visser, Friedrich and Brijlal, (2007: 614) as a structured transmission of entrepreneurial skills, which includes the concepts and mental awareness used by individuals during the conception and management of their businesses. Researchers such as Antonites and Van Vuuren (2005:257) agree that entrepreneurial education stimulates and facilitates entrepreneurial activities.

Entrepreneurship education enhances the development of skills, behaviours and attitudes needed to create jobs and generate economic growth (The World Economic Forum, 2013). Managing is one of the most important human

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activities. From the time human beings began forming social organizations to accomplish aims and objectives they could not accomplish as individuals, managing has been essential to ensure the coordination of individual efforts. As society continuously relied on group effort, and as many organized groups have become large, the task of managers has been increasing in importance and complexity. Henceforth, managerial theory has become crucial in the way managers manage complex organizations (Fayol's management theory).

Based on the three main concepts associated with entrepreneurship Education them being the behaviour of the entrepreneur, the processes to be undertaken and the results, there is need to device and enhance management skills to effectively coordinate the three concept with a goal of producing a student with competences in entrepreneurship. It is important to look at how entrepreneurship education is managed across the globe. According to Parker (2009) entrepreneurship is an integral part of economic change and growth. Yet entrepreneurship has only recently come to be regarded as a field of study. A complete view of it recognizes its multi-disciplinary academic underpinnings, drawing from economics, finance, business studies, psychology and other subjects.

This heterogeneous provenance reflects the multi-dimensional nature of entrepreneurship, which partly contributes to the elusiveness of the entrepreneur. Entrepreneurship education should be part of economics education instruction as Greene & Rice (2007:157) state that the child must be exposed to economics concepts that form a cognitive domain in which entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship can be developed. It is in the economic environment that the entrepreneur has relevance. It is important that schools and adult basic education equip young people for the world of work and the world of finance that they will need to enter, either as employees or employers (Maas et al., 2008:164).

In my view the knowledge and skills learner acquire after leaving school is enough for them to start business instead expecting government to provide them with jobs. Acs and Amores (2008:309) state, "Economists have come to recognize the input completing and gap filling capacities of potential entrepreneurial innovation and growth and the significant contribution of innovation and growth to prosperity and economic welfare". If we accept the need to increase entrepreneurial activities within our economy as an entrepreneurial objective through the use of curriculum materials that discover and develop entrepreneurial attributes, thereby increasing the pool of entrepreneurial talent, we must build a framework in which these curriculums reside (Kent, 1990:157). The recognition of the importance of the entrepreneur and the necessity of the markets in which the entrepreneur operates has led many countries to work on perfecting their markets by eliminating barriers to entrepreneurship and other market failures (ACS & Amores, 2008:309).

It is advisable that governments everywhere should intervene indirectly to improve the enabling environment for entrepreneurship and foster an entrepreneurship culture which must change the mind set of society. Such interventions, referred to by Levie and Autio (2008) as framework conditions, could include:

- Education, which can provide a pool of skilled labour, develop entrepreneurial skills in students, and encourage knowledge exchange by building networks and fostering a collaborative economy.
- Access to entrepreneurial finance. Government sponsored entrepreneurship programmes. Political conditions (e.g., government administrative and regulatory regimes). Access to and transfer of Research and Development as well as technology (Lenihan, 2011:329).
- Education for entrepreneurship has two broad dimensions namely awareness and skills. Awareness and skills can both be taught. Through awareness the sub-conscious is stimulated to focus on the

Element of entrepreneurship that exists around you." Skills are specially focused tasks that the learners can be taught to perform." (Kent, 1990:187). Carree, Van Stel and Wennekers (2002:278); ACS and Audretsch (2003) have noted that, "there is a positive correlation between economic growth and entrepreneurship." Furthermore, empirical research by Benzing, Chu, and Kara (2009:60) concluded that entrepreneurial activities have a significant impact on the growth of the economy.

This notwithstanding, further research has highlighted the bureaucratic challenges, complexities and expenses in government policies and regulations that affect entrepreneurship immensely in a number of countries (World Bank, 2013). Education as a source for knowledge production and skilled personnel is very influential in the economy of any country. There is a need in South Africa to address the employability of school leavers in the development of innovative entrepreneurship education by educational institutions. In order to promote skilled opportunity-oriented entrepreneurs, learners must be exposed to entrepreneurship activities in schools (Govender, 2008:90).

Govender's study explores the application of Junior Enterprise in South African Higher Education Institutions Universities. The study noted that 92% of the learners suggested that the Junior Enterprise concept has the potential to be adapted and applied at universities and 63% felt that there is a need for long-term relationships between the world of work and the university in order to increase students' exposure to practical work experience (Govender, 2008:40). It is clear that the educational level of an individual is very crucial in the probability of both necessity and opportunity driven business ventures. However, Turton and Herrington (2012:34) contend that the effect of educational level works in the opposite direction in each of the categories.

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For example, the probability of an individual being involved in opportunity entrepreneurship rises significantly with increasing educational attainment and the contrary is true for necessity entrepreneurship. Comparing Zambia to other developing countries, Turton and Herrington (2012:34) found that among the young adults' school leavers, the proportion involved in new firm activity is only 1%, whereas in other developing countries it is at least three times higher. The discovery of risk takers, ground breakers, and innovative entrepreneurs is a way through which the Zambian economy can be rejuvenated and unemployment curbed (Davies, 2001:24).

Thus, appropriate professional and academic training that provides entrepreneurial skills is essential. However, Elmuti, Houry, and Omran (2012:97) are of the opinion that entrepreneurship education should consist of content that is innovative and reflective in order to be able to enhance the successes of new business ventures. This study looked at implementing entrepreneurship training at the early learning stages of the youth development phase secondary Schools. The single most important contribution education can do to a child's development is to help him towards a field where his talents best suit him and where he will be satisfied and competent.

We should spend less time ranking children and more time to help them identify their natural gifts, talents and competencies and cultivate those (Bolton & Thompson, 2000:42). The greater the talent possessed, the quicker the learning process is completed. Entrepreneurial education and training is one factor that can have a significant impact on entrepreneurial attitudes and aspirations. One of the biggest challenges facing teachers today is the finding, nurturing and developing of talent. Our education methods and our culture are the main obstacles (Bolton & Thompson, 2000:43). Teachers are so busy surviving and getting through the syllabus that they forget to find and nurture the talent of the learners in their classes. In my view teachers are supposed to guide properly the learners on the areas they can concentrate depending on their strength identified by teachers. Talent then stays dormant and is never or rarely ever developed. Within a classroom there is an amazing mix of talent, but we as teachers fail to harness it, because we fail to recognize it (Bolton & Thompson, 2000:43).

Management Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education
Despite the tremendous growth in entrepreneurship education around the world, there are still many challenges that are hindering the management of the subject. One of the predominant challenges is to address the culture and mind set in countries and regions around the world in which business and entrepreneurship are either not viewed favourably or are not understood. The low exposure to business and entrepreneurship, combined with the lack of role models, makes the barriers to entry in many countries seemingly high. Entrepreneurship education can help promote an entrepreneurial and innovative culture by changing mind sets and providing the necessary skills. At

the same time, there is no "one size fits all" solution for entrepreneurship education.

The challenges and opportunities for entrepreneurship vary dramatically in different parts of the world as well as for different segments of the educational journey. It is not appropriate to import models from other parts of the world without modification. Local context must be taken into account in devising and tailoring a set of programmes and initiatives relevant for each area. Entrepreneurship is still trying to secure its academic credibility, which can create difficulties in efforts to embed entrepreneurship into the school systems. Securing the support of the heads of the academic institutions as well as the governments, which are often the primary funders, is critical. Often within academia, champions of entrepreneurship have to fight internal battles for support and funding of their activities. In most countries, the bulk of the funding for schools and universities still comes from governments, although this is beginning to change as companies, foundations and alumni have begun to contribute.

The field of entrepreneurship education is still relatively young and it is therefore important and necessary that public and private support is continued until entrepreneurship is embedded in a sustainable manner in schools and universities as well as through informal education systems. Entrepreneurship has never been more important than at this time to solve our pressing global challenges. Embedding entrepreneurship in education and providing greater access are the first and arguably most important steps for building an innovative culture and creating a new wave of entrepreneurs, entrepreneurial individuals and organizations. Owhutu (2010), Njoku (2010) and Babalola (2006) have identified the following as challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria: this concern has been related to instability of the academic calendar, infrastructural decay and obsolescence of equipment in the face of population explosion and academic staff shortage among others. Other challenges identified include; Lack of Access to higher education especially university education; Absence of inadequate and functional Curriculum;

Teacher number, quality & welfare still major problems, i.e., they are prevalent of large class sizes and less wages for teachers. No amount of money paid to teachers is too much and Limited school inspections by the superintending agency. Also in the five school visited the study revealed the following challenges in the management of entrepreneurship education; negative attitude by the learners to do the subjects; lack of specialized rooms to do the practical's; inadequate funding from government to procure equipment for the practical's; lack of initiative by some head teachers to initiate programs that promote entrepreneurship education; poor staffing and inadequate teaching and learning materials.

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Conclusion

The literature review highlighted how entrepreneurship is managed globally, at continental level and in Zambian secondary schools. The intervention that were there to promote the subject from different countries and the challenges encountered in the management of entrepreneurship education were discussed.

III. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Introduction

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations based on empirical findings in chapter four.

Conclusions.

The study has shown that entrepreneurship education is offered through the practical subjects such as design and technology, fashion and fabrics, agricultural science, sports and physical education in Zambia while in Austria it is offered through Geography and Economics. These are the subjects that are theory based and have a practical component for the Zambian situation. Our area of concern is that of the practical part where the knowledge and skills acquired from school arrangement can be applied by learners after they leave school.

They must be able to start their own businesses instead of looking to government for employment. Once the mindset of these learners changes from that of looking for employment from government to that of self-employment then we expect the economy of the country to improve. Entrepreneurs contribute to the economic development of the country. It is important that government pumps a lot of funding to small medium and micro enterprise as this group has a great impact to the improvement of the economy. This study concludes that the negative attitude by some head teachers was real as it evident from the respondents. Releasing funds for practical subjects was not easy while no practical subjects received much attention. Also lack of interest among the learners is another sad part, government is trying to promote the subject with meager resources of late modern equipment was supplied to a few schools but very few pupils are interested in the subject.

Recommendations

Entrepreneurship education is recognized as vehicle for economic development of any country in the world. It is for this reason that governments around the world have seen the importance entrepreneurship education and pumping huge sums of money just to try and support this sector. There is need for Ministry of General Education to put deliberate training programs for head teachers so that they can see the importance and start appreciating the subject. In view of these facts, and based on the findings of the study, the following are the recommendations that Government and head teachers can observe;

- Government should start releasing school grants to schools on time and it should increase funding since prices of commodities have gone up.

- Head teachers should have a lot of sensitization meetings and workshops in order for them to appreciate the entrepreneurship education.
- School managements at various levels should be encouraged to initiate activities that are aimed at promoting entrepreneurship education.
- All schools should have careers day at least once per year where successful entrepreneurs can be called and have talks with learners on how they had excelled in their businesses.
- Government together with head teachers must start planning on how to buy modern equipment for entrepreneurship subject instead of relying on obsolete ones.
- Government should always deploy more teachers in entrepreneurship subjects especially in rural schools.
- Head teachers should have a reward policy for both teachers who produce 100% pass rate and pupils who score high marks in entrepreneurship subjects as a way of encouraging more learners to take the subject.
- Entrepreneurship education should be compulsory to all secondary school learners.” Apparently worried by the soaring unemployment rate in Zambia, declining per capita income, youth’s restiveness in various parts of the country, the Federal government directed „ all education institutions in the country to run entrepreneurship studies programme as a compulsory course for all students irrespective of their disciplines. In recognition of the importance of Vocational Subjects, every institution of learning will be required to offer Vocational Subjects as part of their curriculum, (Zambia curriculum framework, 2013). Comparing the two countries the subject is compulsory.

Summary

Chapter 6 ends with the outcomes of the research and offers suggestions for improvements of entrepreneurship education in secondary schools. The chapter closes with recommended areas for future research as well as on how to improve this field of study. This study found that entrepreneurship education is offered in secondary schools through practical subjects, thus entrepreneurial knowledge is being developed. However, the study also found out that despite teaching this subject there is lack of interest among learners to do the subject and even head teachers have negative attitude towards the subject. Thus, the study concluded that various changes to the entrepreneurship education curriculum are required to achieve the goal of entrepreneurship education.

More resources should be channeled to education sector so that modern equipment can be procured by schools. In addition government should go back to old system where it was the responsibility of government to supply text books to schools

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